

THE ROLE OF AUTHENTIC VIDEO IN DEVELOPING SOCIOCULTURAL COMPETENCE

Ataniyazova Dilnoza Shavkatovna

Uzbek State World Languages University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

dilnozshavkatovna@gmail.com

Abstract: The article highlights the history of the development of communicative competence and forming the process of sociocultural competence as a main component of communicative competence. The author describes the features of sociocultural competence and its correlation to using authentic video materials. The advantages and disadvantages of using such materials for educational purposes are analyzed using examples. The recommendations are given on the methodological adaptation of this material to the learning environment.

Keywords: *Authentic material, sociocultural competence, video material, selection of video*

Annotatsiya: Maqolada kommunikativ kompetentsiyaning asosiy tarkibiy qismi sifatida kommunikativ kompetentsiyaning rivojlanish tarixi va ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetensiya jarayonini shakllantirish yoritilgan. Muallif ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetentsiyaning xususiyatlarini va uning haqiqiy video materiallardan foydalanish bilan bog'liqligini tasvirlaydi. Bunday materiallardan o'quv maqsadlarida foydalanishning afzalliklari va kamchiliklari misollar yordamida tahlil qilinadi. Ushbu materialni o'quv muhitiga uslubiy moslashtirish bo'yicha tavsiyalar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: *Haqiqiy material, ijtimoiy-madaniy kompetensiya, video material, video tanlash*

Аннотация: В статье освещена история развития коммуникативной компетентности и процесс формирования социокультурной компетентности как основного компонента коммуникативной компетентности. Автор описывает особенности социокультурной компетентности и ее соотношение с использованием аутентичных видеоматериалов. На примерах анализируются преимущества и

недостатки использования таких материалов в образовательных целях. Даны рекомендации по методической адаптации данного материала к среде обучения.

Ключевые слова: Аутентичный материал, социокультурная компетентность, видеоматериал, подборка видео.

Introducing the communicative competence construct in foreign language acquisition helps to cope with several problems in language teaching. It also is seen as a solution to an important task in the achievement of functional abilities in the target language of learners. “Competence” was first mentioned by Labov in 1966 as a reflection on Chomsky’s theory of “an ideal speaker-listener” that provoked great interest of scientists to the structure of communicative competence.

Canale & Swain (1980) outlined their understanding of communicative competence which includes four areas of knowledge: grammatical competence, sociolinguistic competence, discourse competence and strategic competence. In addition, Krashen (1981) states that: “Language acquisition is very similar to the process children use in acquiring first and second languages. Communicative competence has always been viewed as a complex phenomenon, formed by two to five components according to various scientific approaches. Sociolinguistic competence has been the subject of many studies (Lum 2004, Belenyuk 2008, Koester 2009) where the authors consider the process of occurrence, development and modern concept of sociolinguistic competence, clarify its essence and component composition; determine the importance of the formation of communicative competence.

“This competence is a set of linguistic and non-linguistic (non-verbal) means of communication, as well as the learner’s ability to choose and use them to fit a specific communicative situation and sociocultural norms of society”. Sociolinguistic competence includes sociocultural competence that provides the ability to recognize the national characteristics of the country of the language studied and behave accordingly in situations

with native speakers. Language learners should be introduced to language patterns but the main sociolinguistic, sociocultural phenomenon should be paid specific attention.

Linguistic markers of social relations: the use and choice of forms of greeting, addressing, conversation, the use and choice of exclamations, interjections, parasitic words, etc. thanks, intentional disregard for the formulas of politeness; expressions of folk wisdom: proverbs, sayings, idioms, signs, clichés, evaluative statements. Registers of communication: formal, neutral, informal. Dialect and accent (lexicon, grammar, phonology, vocal characteristics (rhythm, loudness of speech), paralinguistic, sign language) of social classes, regional and national origins, ethnic groups, groups professional activities. Main speech communication conventions in a foreign language society; willingness to overcome the influence of stereotypes and to carry out intercultural dialogue in the general and professional areas of communication.

The classifications of linguistic markers of social relations diverge widely in different languages and cultures depending on such factors as social status, the level of closeness of human relationships, and speech styles. The forms of etiquette are also different in different countries and can become a source of inter-ethnic misunderstanding with misinterpretation. To avoid such kind of misunderstandings in communication with native speakers' language learners should master sociocultural knowledge about the country of the language being studied.

To develop sociocultural competence, a foreign language learner needs to acquire certain knowledge about the lifestyle, traditions and customs of a foreign language speaker, develop the ability to choose and use adequate language forms and means depending on the purpose and situation of communication, and the social roles of communication participants. Not every plot recorded on live video can be used for teaching and learning purposes. When selecting authentic videos for their use in the development and improvement of communication competence, it is necessary to be guided by several criteria.

Authentic video materials demonstrate the process of foreign cultural communication and provide inexhaustible resources for analyzing cultural realities and characteristic features of human actions in various circumstances of interpersonal communication. Moreover, the cognitive activity of students, their aspiration to learn a foreign language and culture increases when authentic video materials are used in English lessons and encourage independent activity in this language. Students have an interest in the learning process, and they have a positive attitude to the perception of the video material [8].

The success of authentic video materials usage in teaching English depends on the effective organization of work with them. At the stage of material selection, it is advisable to determine the educational goals and objectives of using a certain material. The problem of choosing the video material to use for educational purposes is of paramount importance for teachers. It is important to choose the material by the specific task of the lesson. The task of the teacher when selecting video material is to focus on the fact that students are not only interested in the plot but also fascinated by the process of understanding the language. It is safe to say that the effectiveness of a foreign language lesson using video materials depends on the teacher's preliminary preparation for the lesson. The effectiveness of the usage of video materials is determined by the rationality of the organization of this lesson structure, in other words, it depends on how well the capabilities of the video are coordinated with the tasks of the educational process [7].

Conclusion

To conclude we can say that in the process of achieving the stated objective and solving the tasks, the proposed **hypothesis** was confirmed and the following **results** were obtained:

1. The study of the concept of «cross-cultural competence" allowed us to interpret it as the ability of a person to communicate fruitfully with representatives of other cultures

using the language being studied. Cross-cultural competence is an independent competence, and during its formation, a foreign language is not a goal, but a means.

2. In the process of analysis of various models of cross-cultural competence, its main components are identified: the "knowledge" component, the "skills" component and the "relationships" component. These components will be considered an integral part of the content of teaching students the skills of cross-cultural communication.

The development and improvement of these methods led to the creation of completely new didactic materials in form and content, such as filmstrips, film fragments, and films, as well as to the creation of a new means of teaching foreign languages - educational television.

References

1. Bilyalova A., ICT in Teaching a Foreign Language in High School// Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences 237p (2017) 175 – 181pp available at: <https://reader.elsevier.com>
2. Canale, M. & M. Swain (1980). Theoretical bases of communicative approaches to second language teaching and testing. Applied Linguistics 1: 1-47.
3. Krashen S.D. (1981). Second Language Acquisition and Second Language Learning.-Oxford: Pergamon Press Inc.
4. Lum D. Cultural Competence, Practice Stages, and Client Systems: A Case Study Approach. Cengage Learning, 2004.
5. Lustig M.W., Koester J. Intercultural Competence: Interpersonal Communication Across Cultures. Pearson, 2009.
6. Labov, W. (1966). The social stratification of English in New York City. Washington, D.C.: Center for Applied Linguistics Zhoglina. G.G.: Dis.PhD. G.G. Zhoglina.- Pjatig
7. H. Suchankova, Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences, 171, 56-59 (2015) doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.01.088
8. L. Bajrami, M. Ismaili, Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences, 232, 502-506 (2016) doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2016.10.068